

Synthesis and antibacterial studies of novel hydrazide based thorium(IV) and lanthanum(III) complexes

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Abstract : Novel complexes of thorium(IV) and lanthanum(III) have been synthesized by their action with triphenylphosphinimino-*N* group ligands, namely (i) *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)acetohydrazide and (ii) *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)nicotinohydrazide. The present work describes the studies on the coordination behaviour of all these complexes and they have been characterized by the FT-IR, ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectroscopic techniques. Further these complexes were tested against antibacterial activities.

Keywords : Thorium(IV) complexes, lanthanum(III) complexes, hydrazide ligand, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The recent progress in the last five years of organo-f-element chemistry¹ on applications such as homogeneous catalysis and to a lesser extent, materials science especially in organolanthanide research is a continuing trend. However the extraction and separation of many actinides (An^{III}) and lanthanides (Ln^{III}) from the nuclear waste have been a synthetic goal for some time. In this aspect, many Schiff base ligands² and phosphine oxides³ which can readily react with oxophilic metals and f-metals to give remarkable coordination complexes were reported⁴. Novel CMPO-functionalized task specific ionic liquids⁵ were used in selective extraction of actinides and lanthanides. Particularly on the separation of Am^{III} from Eu^{III} was efficiently carried out by extending the range of multicoordinate actinide ligands⁶. By varying several ligands on An^{III} and Ln^{III} complexes their stability and thermal studies were investigated⁷.

Apart from these, we are interested in an exploration of our triphenylphosphinimino donor system as bidentate ligands with lanthanides and actinides. However, the La^{III} and Th^{IV} complexes involving novel phosphinimino donor ligands have not been synthesized as yet, which prompted us to carry such type of investigations because

of their versatility, structural characteristics, stability, reactivity and applications. The resulting complexes are also of interest for possible biological activity and they were tested against bacterial species like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as a criterion for the antibacterial studies.

Results and discussion

The coordination compounds (**3-6**) of the general composition XML₂ [X = (NO₃)₄; Cl₃] were synthesized on reaction of metals (M = Th and La) with the bidentate triphenylphosphinimino donor ligands L = -OC(R) = NN(=PPh₃)-, where R = CH₃, 3-pyridyl (Scheme 1). The complexes obtained were stable in the presence of air and moisture and they are soluble in methanol, DMSO and partially soluble in chloroform. The stretching band ν(C=O) was absent for the complexes **3-6** in the infrared spectrum, due to formation of ν(C-O) stretching vibration at the region ~1120 cm⁻¹ through tautomerization mechanism indicating the formation of chelate complex which was further confirmed by the appearance of another band at ~1630 cm⁻¹ for ν(C=N)⁸. ³¹P NMR spectra of complexes (**3-6**) showed the chemical shifts towards downfield compared to the free ligand signals (Table 1) and substantial shifts in the ¹H NMR were observed

Scheme 1

Table 1. FT-IR and ³¹P NMR data of compounds 1-6

Compd.	Infrared stretching frequency (cm ⁻¹)				³¹ P NMR (ppm)	
	N-H	C=O	P=N	C=N	N-N	
1	3458.44	1631.78 ^a (C=O)	1190.08	-	997.20	29.77
2	3442.94	1687.71 ^a (C=O)	1273.02	-	968.27	29.34
3	-	1124.30	1273.02	1635.64	927.76	33.74
4	-	1124.30	1255.60	1635.64	997.20	31.44
5	-	1120.64	1192.01	1629.85	923.90	32.66
6	-	1120.64	1273.02	1629.85	939.33	30.46

^aCorresponds to C=O stretching.

for the complexes (3-6) from the ligands (1, 2), which are considerably deshielded. The shifts in the resonance of ¹³C NMR for the complexes (3-6) from the range of C=O (160-185 ppm) to C=N (145-160 ppm) reveals the conversion of keto group to imine group.

Antibacterial activity results :

The obtained antibacterial results are given in Table 1 comparing to the standard antibiotic, Niacin. The antibacterial activity is dependent on the concentration of the tested compounds and thus it concludes that, these compounds inhibit the growth of bacteria to a greater extent as the concentration is increased. The most sensitive bacterial species on compounds tested is Gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus*, while Gram-negative bacteria *P. aeruginosa* is the most resistant species. The complexes containing 3-pyridyl substituted ligands (4, 6) have shown more activity against tested bacterial species than their isostructural complexes containing methyl substituents (3, 5).

Experimental

Materials :

The chemicals such as thorium nitrate pentahydrate

Table 2. Inhibition zone data from antibacterial investigations of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Conc. (mg/ml)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
3	5	-	++	-
	10	+++	+	+
4	5	+	-	+
	10	++	+++	++
5	5	-	++	-
	10	++	+	-
6	5	-	-	-
	10	++++	+	+++
Niacin	5	+++	++	++
	10	++++	++++	+++

++++ = 20-25 mm, +++ = 15-20 mm, ++ = 10-15 mm, + = 5-10 mm and - = Zilch.

and lanthanum trichloride heptahydrate were purchased from Loba and Sd Fine Chemicals and used as such without further purification. Methanol, chloroform, THF and pet. ether were purchased from Sd Fine Chemicals and were purified by standard procedures.

Instrumentation :

¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectra were determined in CDCl₃ solutions at 400 MHz respectively using the Bruker Ascend Model. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1 spectrophotometer.

Synthetic methodology :

Ligand synthesis : The ligands 1 and 2 were synthesized in the laboratory according to the reported methodology⁹ from their respective hydrazides.

N-(Triphenylphosphoranylidene)acetohydrazide (1) : Pale yellow color solid. Yield : 85%; m.p. : 155-158 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3456.44 (N-H), 2920.64 (C-H), 1190.08 (P=N), 1631.78 (C=O), 997.20 (N-N); ¹H NMR : δ 1.690 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.44-7.69 (15H, m, Ph); ¹³C NMR :

δ 20.92 (CH₃), 128.55–133.03 (Ph), 162.08 (C=O); ³¹P NMR δ : 29.77. *N*-(Triphenylphosphoranylidene)-nicotinohydrazide (**2**) : Brown color solid. Yield : 68%; m.p. 57–60 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3442.94 (N-H), 1273.02 (P=N), 1687.71 (C=O), 1625.99 (C=C), 937.40 (N-N); ¹H NMR δ : 7.30–7.55 (15H, m, Ph), 3-pyridyl δ 7.66 (1H, s), 8.74, 8.75 (1H, d), 7.60, 7.61, 7.62 (1H, t), 7.70 (1H); ¹³C NMR : δ 123.29–142.30 (Ar), 153.1 (C=N, Ar), 169.01 (C=O); ³¹P NMR : δ 29.94.

General protocol for synthesis of complexes 3-6 : Metal salts [Th(NO₃)₄.5H₂O or LaCl₃.7H₂O] were dissolved in 30 mL of methanol and their respective ligands (**1**, **2**) were added to the solution. The mixture was allowed to stir for 24 h at room temperature and it is observed that the solutions were changed completely to different colours based on the substituent(s) on the ligands. Then the solvent was removed by rotavapour and the isolated solids were washed with n-hexane before drying with high vacuum pump.

Dichloro bis *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)-acetohydrazide lanthanum(III) chloride (**3**) : Colourless crystalline solid. Yield : 0.271 g (78.3%); m.p. 132–135 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 2920.23 (C-H), 1120.64 (C-O), 1192.01 (P=N), 1629.85 (C=N), 923.90 (N-N); ¹H NMR : δ 1.420 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.35–7.60 (30H, m, Ph); ¹³C NMR : δ 21.15 (CH₃), 125.60–132.94 (Ph), 155.33 (N=C); ³¹P NMR δ : 33.74. Dichloro bis *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)nicotinohydrazide lanthanum(III) chloride (**4**) : Reddish brown color solid. Yield : 0.391 g (81%); m.p. 157–158 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3055.24 (C-H), 1120.64 (C-O), 1273.02 (P=N), 1629.85 (C=N), 1589.34 (C=C), 939.33 (N-N); ¹H NMR δ : 7.43–7.54 (30H, m, Ph), 3-pyridyl δ 9.20 (1H, s), 8.74, 8.75 (1H, d), 7.61, 7.62, 7.65 (1H, t); ¹³C NMR : δ 121.90–140.92 (Ar), 161.6 (O-C=N), 151.7 (C=N, Ar); ³¹P NMR δ : 31.44. Bis *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)acetohydrazide thorium(IV) nitrate : Pale yellow color solid. Yield : 0.255 g (52.6%); m.p. 252–254 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 2875.86 (C-H), 1124.30 (C-O), 1273.02 (P=N), 1635.64 (C=N), 927.76 (N-N); ¹H NMR δ : 1.510 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.44–7.69 (30H, m, Ph); ¹³C NMR δ : 25.6 (CH₃), 125.6–137.0 (Ph), 157.6 (N=C); ³¹P NMR δ : 32.66. Bis *N*-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)nicotinohydrazide thorium(IV) nitrate (**6**) : Brown color solid, Yield : 0.334 g (76%); m.p. 245 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3066.82 (C-H), 1124.30 (C-O), 1255.66

(P=N), 1635.64 (C=N), 1523.76 (C=C), 997.20 (N-N); ¹³C NMR δ : 120.82–139.8 (Ar), 150.6 (C=N, Ar), 160.5 (O-C=N); ³¹P NMR δ : 30.46.

Antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activities were tested with the three bacteria : one Gram-positive [*Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923)] and two Gram-negative [*Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 25619)], against synthesized compounds (**3-6**) by using the agar well diffusion method¹⁰. The bacteria were used as inoculums from the cultures of nutrient agar medium. Whatmann filter paper discs (diameter 6.5 mm) were saturated with the solutions of test compound (concentration : 5 and 10 mg/mL) or reference drug, Niacin (conc : 5 and 10 mg/ml). By the measurement of zone of inhibition (ZOI) around the wells after 24 h of incubation at 37 °C determines antibacterial activity. The diameter of the zone was measured (in mm) and compared with that of positive and negative control. The experiment was performed in duplicates and each of the readings was taken by two observers and the average was calculated.

Conclusion

In summary, some novel lanthanum(III) (**3**, **4**) and thorium(IV) (**5**, **6**) complexes based on phosphiminohydrazides were reported. The complexes (**3-6**) were characterized by spectroscopic techniques like FT-IR, ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR. Compounds **3-6** were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activities and found that complexes bearing 3-pyridyl substituent, exhibited better activities toward tested bacteria than those containing methyl moiety.

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